
Study on Cellulose Sponges Reinforced by Viscose Rayon Fibers

Noerati ^{1*}, Ika Natalia Mauliza ¹, and Riska Pramana Putri ¹

¹ Politeknik STTT Bandung

* Correspondence: noeratikemal@gmail.com; Tel.: +62-8103-141-513

Abstract: Cellulose sponges are an example of fiber-reinforced polymer composites. In the past few years, natural materials were considered to replace synthetic materials in the manufacture of sponges. These cellulose sponges have high water absorption which can be used as an absorbent. In this study, cellulose sponges were made from cellulose xanthate as a matrix and cellulose fibers as reinforcement with variations in reinforcement concentrations of 1%, 2%, 3%, 4%, and 5%. Sponge morphology, tensile strength, elongation, and water absorption for 2 and 24 hours of immersion were characterized. The morphology of cellulose sponges shows a thick layer that has cavities inside which is caused by melting glauber salt. The more viscose rayon fibers in the cellulose sponge, the higher the tensile strength of the cellulose sponge and the smaller the elongation at break. The water absorption of cellulose sponge is more than 100%. However, addition of viscose rayon did not significantly influence the absorption.

Keywords: absorbency, cellulose sponges, fiber-reinforced polymer composite, viscose rayon

DOI :

1. Introduction

Cellulose sponge is an example of a fiber reinforced polymer composite. In the last few years, the manufacture of sponges made from natural materials had been considered to replace synthetic materials. The consideration is based on the cellulose sponges which are more environmentally friendly than plastic because they can be decomposed in landfills.

Cellulose sponges are used in the health industry and cosmetics. They are generally used for absorption and cleaning [1]. Some other uses of cellulose sponges are for soundproofing, biological culture media, bioreactors and adhesive plasters [2]. Cellulose sponges are soft in wet condition which make less damage on a properties, can be made and printed in various forms, and can be decomposed easily in soil by microbe [2, 3]. The heat resistance is better than that of the urethane

sponge, and the physical properties will not be changed up to about a hundred forty degrees centigrade(140°). Making cellulose sponges can be carried out with polyurethane foam and viscose rayon methods, while polyurethane methods from wood liquefied in polyhydric alcohols and viscose rayon used NMMO or CS₂ as a solvents [3], [4]. Nobuhiro [5] identified the manufacture of cellulose sponges in 1998, but at that time the manufacture of cellulose sponges did not use reinforcing fibers. The use of reinforcing fibers in the manufacture of cellulose sponges aims to improve the mechanical properties of cellulose sponges. The reinforcing fibers can be obtained from natural fibers or synthetic fibers. Sugeng Waluyo [6] made cellulose sponges by utilizing cotton fibers as reinforcing fibers. The matrix with a fiber composition of 25% produced a sponge that can absorb water by 2.5 times its dry weight.

In this study, cellulose sponges were made from regenerated cellulose in the form of xanthate cellulose reinforced with viscose rayon fibers. The basic components of cellulose sponges are natural polymers in the form of regenerated cellulose polymers that can be decomposed by microorganism (biodegradable). It is very suitable for sponge production because they are hydrophilic, renewable and biodegradable. Cellulose sponges have good prospects to replace synthetic sponges that are not easily decomposed by microorganisms.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Cellulose xanthate and viscose rayon fibers were obtained from PT South Pacific Viscose., Glauber salt (Na₂SO₄.10H₂O p.a.), NaOH p.a. 6%, H₂SO₄ p.a. 6%.

2.2. Method

Cellulose xanthate solution is made from pulp base material of the same quality to make viscose rayon fibers which had been processed through alkalization, ageing, xanthation, and ripening [7]. The viscose rayon staple fiber is placed on the vessel bottom. The polymer solution of cellulose xanthate was mixed with 6% NaOH into a beaker glass then stirred. After being homogeneous, Glauber salts (Na₂SO₄.10H₂O) was then added and stirred well. Then it was poured into a vessel containing viscose rayon fiber 1%, 2%, 3%, 4%, and 5% (w/w). Cellulose xanthate polymers and viscose rayon fibers were mixed together and molded. After that, it was heated at 100°C for 2 hours. The samples were then rinsed with water at room temperature, followed by dipping in 6% sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) for 30 minutes. Finally, the samples were washed and dried in the oven for 60 minutes at 120°C.

2.3. Characterization

Morphology of the samples was observed under a microscope with 40 times magnification. Absorption and tensile strength were tested according to ASTM D 570 – 98 [8] and ASTM D 638-14 [9], respectively.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Morphology of cellulose sponges

Morphology of cellulose sponges are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Morphology of cellulose sponges are shown

Morphological images of cellulose sponges showed layers with cavities. In the fabricating process, Glauber salt was used. During heating, cellulose xanthate became solids, and Glauber salt (as Sodium sulfate decahydrate) melted at 32.38°C [10] and then dissolved in water leaving empty cavity when the temperature reaches 100°C. Glauber salt crystals caused the forming of the cavities (pores) in the cellulose xanthate polymer matrix, solidified the cellulose xanthate upon salting out mechanism. Salting out is the process of adding electrolyte solution into the water phase containing organic compounds. The electrolyte solution was added in order to make the solubility of organic compounds in water decreases and the concentration of organic compounds in the organic phase would be greater than in the water phase. Precipitation in the salting-out process occurred because there was a competition between salt and organic polymers, in this case, cellulose to bind water molecules. Ions on the surface of organic substances attract many water molecules and bind strongly [11], [12]. Sodium sulfate added to the cellulose polymer solution will be attracted by water molecules. This is because salt ions have a greater charge density than cellulose polymers. The ionic strength of salt at high concentrations gets stronger so that the salt can more easily to bind attracted by water molecules [3]. The decrease in the amount of water bound to cellulose polymers causes the attraction between the molecules of cellulose polymers to be stronger compared to the attractive forces between cellulose and water polymer molecules (enhancing hydrophobic interactions) therefore, cellulose polymers will settle into cellulose sponges. Soaking with a 6% H₂SO₄ solution was to convert cellulose xanthate into cellulose with the reaction mechanism which presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Transformation of cellulose xanthate into cellulose [7]

3.2. Tensile strength and elongation cellulose sponges

The addition of viscose rayon fibers as reinforcement to the cellulose matrix affects the mechanical properties of cellulose sponges as presented in Figures 3 and 4. The more the viscose rayon fibers in cellulose sponges, the higher the tensile strength of cellulose sponges and the smaller the elongation of a cellulose sponge.

Figure 3. The effect of reinforcement fiber to the tensile strength of the cellulose sponges

Addition of viscose fiber in cellulose xanthate solution can increase the tensile strength of cellulose sponge. This is because the load received by cellulose sponges can be distributed evenly on viscose fibers. Thus, the more viscose fibers in the sponge resulted the higher the tensile strength of the sponge. The presence of viscose rayon fibers causes the interfacial bonding of the hydrogen bond in the regenerated cellulose polymer matrix and viscose rayon fibers so that the cellulose sponge becomes strong [6].

Figure 4. The effect of reinforcement fiber to the elongation of the cellulose sponges

Addition of viscose rayon fibers will reduce the elongation at break of the cellulose sponges. This is because viscose rayon fibers have higher molecular orientation than the cellulose matrix. More regular molecular chain arrangement on viscose rayon fibers plays an important role in decreasing the elongation at break of cellulose sponges.

3.3. Absorption of cellulose sponges

Figure 5 shows the effect of adding viscose rayon reinforcing fibers to the absorption of cellulose sponges.

Figure 5. The effect of reinforcement fiber to the absorption of the cellulose sponges

These sponges have the ability to absorb more than 100% water. Viscose rayon fibers in the cellulose sponges tend to reduce water absorption. However, the decrease in absorption is not significant. The addition of 5% viscose fiber can only reduced 7% of absorption capacity compared to the addition of

1% viscose rayon fibers. The decrease in absorption of cellulose sponges with the addition of viscose rayon fibers is caused by the more tightly ordered molecular chain viscose rayon fibers. In fact, that viscose rayon fibers are fibers that have sufficient absorption capacity, however, the addition of viscose rayon fibers does not cause a substantial decrease in absorption. Thus, the addition of viscose rayon fibers does not significantly reduce the absorption of cellulose sponges.

4. Conclusion

The morphology of cellulose sponges have cavities which are caused by the melting of Glauber salts. Viscose rayon fibers as reinforcement of the sponges tend to increase the tensile strength and reduce the fiber elongation of the cellulose sponge but they do not have too much influence on the tensile strength of cellulose sponges.

References

- [1] S. Applications, "Cellulose Fibre-Reinforced Biofoam for," pp. 1–10.
- [2] "High Performance Materials, Cellulose sponge," *Toray Chemistry*, 2016. [Online]. Available: <http://www.torayfinechemicals.com/english>. [Accessed: 12-Mar-2019].
- [3] Ryan Coda, "A Study of Cellulose Based Biodegradable Foams and Sponges," Georgia Institute of Technology, 2005.
- [4] M. Halidan and K. Bzuor, "Preparation of cellulose sponge by cellulose urethane method," *CIESC J.*, vol. 63 (5), pp. 1637–1642, 2012.
- [5] S. Yamaguchi, "Cellulose Sponge and Method of Manufacturing Same," EP0837091A1, 1998.
- [6] S. Waluyo, A. Widiadi, and Burhansyah, "Studi Awal Pembuatan Spons Selulosa," in *Prosiding Simposium Nasional POLimer II*.
- [7] P. S. P. V. Training Center, *Fiber Process*. Purwakarta: PT South Pacific Viscose, 2017.
- [8] A. Internasional, "ASTM D 570-98 Standard Test Methods For Water Absorption of Plastics." Philadelphia, 1998.
- [9] A. Internasional, "ASTM D 638-14 : Standard Test Methods For Tensile Properties Of Plastics." ASTM Internasional, 2014.
- [10] Ö. Gök, M. Ö. Yilmaz, and H. Ö. Paksoy, "Stabilization of Glauber's Salt for Latent Heat Storage," pp. 1–10, 2004.
- [11] L. Lee, *Molecular Thermodynamics of Electrolyte Solutions*. Toh Tuck Link: World Scientific Publishing Co. Pte. Ltd., 2008.
- [12] R. Sadeghi and F. Jahani, "Salting-In and Salting-Out of Water-Soluble Polymers in Aqueous Salt Solutions Supporting Information," *J. Phys. Chem. B*, vol. 116, pp. 5234–5241, 2012.